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Research Article

**THE PREVALENCE OF LEFT VENTRICULAR DIASTOLIC
DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE PULMONARY
EMBOLISM AND ITS IMPACT ON PROGNOSIS: A
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Abstract

Background: Heart failure, mainly systolic dysfunction, has been studied as a determining factor in the prognosis of patients with acute pulmonary embolism (PE). However, left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) has not been well studied in this regard.

Methods: A total of 516 patients were diagnosed with acute PE from January 2013 to December 2016. Both hemodynamically stable and unstable patients (i.e. massive PE) who underwent echocardiography within two months of diagnosis were included. Of these, 161 patients were finally included in the study. A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted to investigate the prevalence of LVDD in patients with acute PE and its influences on in-hospital mortality or poor clinical outcomes.

Results: Of 161 patients, 35 patients died during hospitalization (mortality rate 21.7%). Among 73 patients without left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, 14 died (mortality rate 19.2%). Among 88 patients with left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, 21 died (mortality rate 23.9%). The odds ratio of mortality in these patients was 1.321 (0.617 to 2.828), with 95% confidence intervals ($P = 0.473$).

Conclusions: In patients with acute PE, LVDD identified by echocardiography was associated with higher in-hospital mortality rates (23.9 compared with 19.2 for those without LVDD), although this effect was not statistically significant. Additional studies with a larger sample size are required to fully clarify the prognostic effects of LVDD on patients with acute PE.

Keywords: pulmonary embolism, heart failure, diastolic dysfunction, prevalence, mortality.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute pulmonary embolism (PE) is a common medical condition associated with significant morbidity and mortality. In the United States, sudden death is the first symptom in about 25% of patients who present with PE.¹ Predictions of prognosis and mortality of PE vary extensively. Analysis of PE mortality trends and comorbidities may reveal how effectively the disease is treated and prevented, as well as aiding in the recognition of other risk factors.

Acute PE is managed mainly by respiratory support and anticoagulation, provided there are no contraindications. In the case of massive PE (i.e. PE with hemodynamic instability) thrombolysis may be indicated.

It is well known that medical comorbidities may have an impact on PE prognosis. The most extensively studied comorbidities are those of cardiovascular origin e.g. right ventricular (RV) dysfunction and left ventricular (LV) systolic dysfunction.²⁻⁴ However, there is a knowledge gap regarding the implications of LV diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) in patients with acute PE.⁵ LVDD is a type of heart failure that is less well recognized than the systolic variety.

The aim of this study was to investigate the prevalence of LVDD among patients with acute PE and the influence of LVDD on the in-hospital mortality in patients with acute PE. This study also investigated the prognostic value of diastolic dysfunction, as assessed by echocardiography, in predicting mortality rates in patients with acute PE. The working hypothesis is that PE affects pulmonary circulation and may therefore decrease the LV preload, leading to LVDD.

Consideration of the information provided by this study will be important in the management of such patients, with the ultimate aim of reducing mortality rates and improving quality of life in this patient population .

METHODOLOGY:

Study Population

In this study, all patients who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were targeted. The inclusion criteria were: (A) patients diagnosed with acute PE, including those who were hemodynamically unstable (i.e. massive PE), during the period from January 2013 to December 2016 and (B) patients over the age of 14. The exclusion criteria were: (A) patients who were not diagnosed using computed tomography (CT) angiography or

ventilation/perfusion scan and (B) patients who did not undergo echocardiography within two months of diagnosis. A total of 161 of 516 patients with acute PE were finally included in the study.

Massive PE is defined in this study as PE with systolic blood pressure (SBP) less than 90 mmHg or a drop in SBP of 40 mmHg or more, in addition to other signs and symptoms supporting the diagnosis including tachycardia, shortness of breath, decreased urine output and altered level of consciousness.

Diastolic dysfunction is diagnosed in this study using echo Doppler and transmitral Doppler indices of diastolic function. The deceleration time and early (E) and late (A) ventricular filling velocities are measured and the E/A ratio is calculated. After that LVDD is divided into mild (E/A ratio greater than 1 and prolonged deceleration time), moderate (E/A ratio greater than 1 and intermediate values of deceleration time) and severe (E/A ratio greater than 1.5 and shortened deceleration time).⁶ In addition to that LV filling pressure was measured, which better determines the signs and symptoms and prognosis of heart failure in diastolic dysfunction.^{7,8}

Study Area and Data Collection

The data collection was performed using paper and electronic patient files and the echocardiography laboratory database of A tertiary center. The information, including the variables under investigation and baseline characteristics, was recorded on the data collection sheets. Each patient was represented by a "subject number" and patient file numbers were saved in another table with their corresponding subject numbers. The study was conducted between 2016 and 2018.

Study Objectives

The main aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of LVDD in patients presenting with acute PE. This study also aimed to assess the prognostic effect of LVDD on the mortality rate in this patient population during the same admission period.

Secondary objectives of this study involved the assessment of adverse effects of LVDD on PE patients, including the need for ICU admission and the use of inotropic agents or thrombolytic therapy as well as the impact of LVDD on the recurrence of PE.

Study Design

A comparative cross-sectional study design was used to estimate the prevalence of LV diastolic

dysfunction in acute PE patients. However, in-hospital mortality and the remainder of secondary objectives were evaluated in a retrospective cohort study.

Sample Size

The sample size for the cohort part of this study was estimated using the OpenEpi website tool (www.openepi.com). Using the Fleiss statistical method with continuity correction, a total sample size of 368 patients was estimated on the basis of the correlating values of a previous similar study.⁵ However, the sample size was limited by the availability of 161 patients with acute PE.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 23. Baseline patient characteristics were compared using the independent samples *t*-test for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical variables. Odds ratios and *P*-values for the risk factors of interest were also calculated. *P* < 0.05 were considered to indicate statistical significance.

Ethical Considerations

Patients' medical records were reviewed in the medical records department only, and patients were

not contacted. Patients' identities are not available for publication and were recorded in the strictest confidence. Patients' data are presented without deception or misrepresentation. This study was approved by the local Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the tertiary center where the study was conducted. As this is a chart review and as per the IRB instructions, no consent was required from patients.

RESULTS:

Baseline Patient Characteristics

A total of 516 patients were admitted with acute PE during the period from January 2013 to December 2016. According to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 161 patients were included in this study. There were statistically significant differences in the baseline characteristics between the groups of PE patients with and without LVDD in terms of age, the incidence of hypertension, diabetes and ischemic heart disease (Table 1). Patients in the diastolic dysfunction group were significantly older (65.7 ± 16.7 y vs. 48.9 ± 18.5 y, *P* < 0.01), and had a higher incidence of hypertension (67.0% vs. 38.4%, *P* = 0.001), diabetes (54.5% vs. 28.8%, *P* = 0.003) and ischemic heart disease (19.3% vs. 4.1%, *P* = 0.009).

Characteristics (161 patients)	Patients without diastolic dysfunction n = 73 (45.3%)	Patients with diastolic dysfunction n = 88 (54.7%)	<i>P</i> -value
Age (years)	48.9 ± 18.535	65.70 ± 16.70	<0.010
Male n(%)	30 (41.1%)	41 (46.6%)	0.484
Height (m)	1.61 ± 0.100	1.65 ± 0.40	0.447
Weight (kg)	74.09 ± 21.880	72.61 ± 18.17	0.641
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.53 ± 8.340	27.76 ± 7.10	0.525
Smoking n (%)	5 (6.8%)	7 (8.0%)	0.934
Alcohol intake n (%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.1%)	0.637
Hypertension n (%)	28 (38.4%)	59 (67.0%)	0.001
Dyslipidemia n (%)	7 (9.6%)	18 (20.5%)	0.144
Diabetes n (%)	21 (28.8%)	48 (54.5%)	0.003
Atrial fibrillation n (%)	6 (8.2%)	5 (5.7%)	0.545
Chronic kidney disease n (%)	6 (8.2%)	10 (11.4%)	0.520
Ischemic heart disease n (%)	3 (4.1%)	17 (19.3%)	0.009
Valvular heart disease n (%)	2 (2.7%)	1 (1.1%)	0.501
Pulmonary hypertension n (%)	7 (9.6%)	5 (5.7%)	0.423

Table 1: Baseline Patient Characteristics

Diastolic Dysfunction on Echocardiography

The majority of the patients included in this study showed evidence of diastolic dysfunction on their echocardiograms, with a prevalence of 54.7% (88 out of 161 patients). Among the 88 patients with LVDD on echocardiography, 78 had mild diastolic dysfunction, five had moderate and five had severe diastolic dysfunction.

Diastolic Dysfunction and Mortality

	Patients without diastolic dysfunction n = 73 (45.3%)	Patients with diastolic dysfunction n = 88 (54.7%)	Odds Ratio (95% Confidence Interval)	P-value
In-hospital death	14 (19.2%)	21 (23.9%)	1.321 (0.617 to 2.828)	0.473
ICU admission required	19 (26.0%)	16 (18.2%)	0.632 (0.297 to 1.341)	0.230
Inotropic agents required	7 (9.6%)	6 (6.8%)	0.69 (0.221 to 2.152)	0.521
Pulmonary embolism recurrence	6 (8.2%)	6 (6.8%)	0.817 (0.252 to 2.650)	0.736
Thrombolytics required	4 (5.5%)	1 (1.1%)	0.198 (0.22 to 1.815)	0.114

Table 2: Mortality Rates and Adverse Clinical Outcomes

Diastolic Dysfunction and Adverse Clinical Outcomes

Assessing adverse clinical outcomes was the secondary objective of this study. Therefore, this study investigated the need for ICU admission, recurrence of PE, the use of inotropic agents (epinephrine and dopamine) and the use of thrombolytic therapy (tissue plasminogen activator or tPA). The number of patients who required admission to the ICU was higher in the group without LVDD (26.0%) compared to those with this condition (18.2%). Similarly, the number of patients who required inotropes was higher in the group without LVDD (9.6%) compared to those with the condition (6.8%). Likewise, the number of patients who required thrombolytic therapy was higher in the group without LVDD (5.5%) compared to those with diastolic dysfunction (1.1%).

DISCUSSION:

Although PE mortality has seen a decline recently, [9] it still remains a major cause of mortality especially among the elderly. [10]

Two primary outcomes were investigated in this study; the prevalence of LV diastolic dysfunction, and the effect of this condition on in-hospital mortality. LVDD was detected in approximately one out every two patients with PE. This is a huge number that

The second major aim of this study was to predict in-hospital mortality during the same period of admission (Table 2). In total, 35 patients died of PE, with a mortality rate of 21.7%. Among the PE patients with LVDD, 21 died, with a mortality rate of 23.9%. Among the patients without LVDD, 14 died, with a mortality rate of 19.2%. The odds ratio was calculated as 1.321, with a 95% confidence interval of 0.617 to 2.828 (P = 0.473).

warrants further investigation. In this study, the prevalence of LVDD in patients with PE was higher than the 21.5% prevalence reported previously.⁵ These values may indicate acute development of LVDD in such patients. It is important to note that baseline echocardiographic data for these patients was unavailable; therefore, this study cannot determine with certainty whether the LVDD was a chronic condition or an acute occurrence.

The adverse clinical outcomes recorded were variable. Regarding in-hospital deaths, the mortality rate increased 1.321-fold among the patients with LVDD compared to those without (Table 2), although this was not statistically significant. Interestingly, the group without LVDD showed higher numbers in ICU admissions, use of inotropic agents and thrombolytics. It can be speculated that these results are caused by the higher incidence of hypertension among the patients with LVDD.

This study was not without its limitations. First, the 1.321-fold increase in in-hospital mortality among the PE patients with LVDD is not statistically significant; this may be due to the relatively small number of patients included in the study. Further studies in larger patient populations are required to obtain a statistically significant result. Second, the two groups of patients were similar in all but four baseline characteristics:

age, comorbid diabetes, hypertension and ischemic heart disease, all of which are independent risk factors for diastolic dysfunction. Third, the echocardiographic data was obtained within two months of the diagnosis of PE, which is considered to be a long period. This could affect the validity of the results.

CONCLUSION:

The results of this study indicate that LVDD is prevalent in 54.7% of patients with acute PE. The in-hospital mortality rate in patients with acute PE is increased by 1.321-fold in the presence of concurrent LVDD, although this result was not statistically

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Conflicts of Interest

No potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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